

GEOPHYSICAL APPROACH FOR GROUNDWATER EXPLORATION IN THE PETRICH REGION: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT. In regions where access to fresh water is compromised, groundwater exploration is only option for the community. The Petrich region, and specifically the village of Mahalata in the Strumyani Municipality, faces a growing challenge in securing reliable and affordable water for domestic use. As part of a sustainable solution, an electrical resistivity tomography study was conducted to identify potential groundwater deposits. This investigation aims to explore rainwater drainage patterns and identify optimal drilling locations for groundwater wells. The aim of the current study is to identify fracture and fault zones where rainwater infiltration can contribute to aquifers.

Key words: Electrical resistivity tomography (ERT), groundwater, geophysics.

ГЕОФИЗИЧЕН ПОДХОД ЗА ПРОУЧВАНЕ НА ПОДЗЕМНИТЕ ВОДИ В РАЙОНА НА ПЕТРИЧ: ПРАКТИЧЕСКО ИЗСЛЕДВАНЕ

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РЕЗЮМЕ. В региони, където има ограничен достъп до прясна вода, изследването на подпочвените води е единствената възможност за осигуряване на битовите нужди. Село Махалата в община Струмьяни е изправено пред нарастващо предизвикателство за осигуряване на надеждна и достъпна вода за битови нужди. Като част от устойчиво решение беше проведено изследване на електротомография, за да се идентифицират потенциални зони с наличие на подземни води. Настоящото изследване има за цел да проучи зоните на дренаж на дъждовна вода и да идентифицира оптималните места за сондиране на кладенци за подпочвени води. Целта на проучването е да идентифицира зоните с напукване и разломните зони, където е възможно да се задържа подпочвена вода.

Ключови думи: Електросъпротивителна томография, подземни води, геофизика.

Introduction

Due to the absence of an affordable and consistent water supply in the village of Mahalata, residents rely on alternative sources, such as limited surface water and rainwater collection. However, these methods do not provide sufficient quantities of water for daily domestic needs. As Igwebuike and his co-workers stated (Igwebuike, et al., 2024), securing groundwater resources is paramount and required a concentrated effort. Groundwater, therefore, represents a crucial untapped resource that could offer a more sustainable solution. Geophysical methods and especially electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) are used to evaluate in non-invasive manner the best zones for accumulation groundwaters. According to Tomova (2023), electrical resistivity tomography is commonly used to solve mining and engineering issues, because it is efficient and environmentally sound. ERT was selected for this investigation due to its effectiveness in mapping subsurface features and providing actual information for observed geological section based on electrical resistivity (Dimovski, et al., 2014, 2017a). As Kisyov and his colleagues mentioned (Kisyov, et al. 2024), Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) is a geophysical technique used to image subsurface structures and variations in electrical resistivity. It is a geophysical imaging method that utilises electrical resistivity measurements to create images of subsurface resistivity variations. The method allows identification of areas with higher likelihood of groundwater accumulation, associated with variations in rock conductivity caused by differences in moisture content and porosity.

Geological Context of the village of Mahalata and the Strumyani Municipality

The occurrence and availability of ground water in the area, is dependent on many different but closely related geologic factors, like rock type, structure, weathering, and topography (Herrick and LeGrand, 1949; Crawford and Kath, 2001, 2003; Kath et al., 2001).

One of the key factors affecting groundwater availability in igneous and metamorphic rocks is the type of rock itself. While this might appear self-evident, it is frequently underestimated in water-resource studies within crystalline rock regions. The rock type plays a crucial role in determining the depth and extent of weathering, as well as influencing the nature of water-bearing fractures and discontinuities that can develop within the bedrock.

The geology of the region is marked by a complex landscape, situated in the southwestern part of Bulgaria. It is characterised by a combination of mountainous terrain and sedimentary basins. The region lies near the Struma River valley, with surrounding mountain ranges, such as the Belasitsa and the Pirin mountains. The geology of the Strumyani Municipality and the broader southwestern Bulgarian region is characterised by a complex interplay of metamorphic rocks, faulting, and alluvial deposits.

The metamorphic rocks, like gneisses, schists, and marbles, dominate the area. These rocks are formed under high pressure and temperature conditions and have been extensively folded and faulted over geological time.

The region can be considered like seismically active due to the presence of significant fault lines. The Struma Fault is one

of the major fault systems running through the valley, contributing to the region's geological complexity and influencing groundwater movement.

Southwestern Bulgaria includes several sedimentary basins, too, formed by the accumulation of alluvial deposits, sands, gravels, and clays. These basins are important for groundwater storage and surface water drainage, making them relevant for rainwater infiltration studies. According to Casas et al. (2007), for unconsolidated sediments, the permeability is strongly related to the clay content, which can be deduced from indirect resistivity methods, like electrical imaging.

The municipality of Strumyani is situated in the Struma River Valley, a key geographical and geological feature of southwestern Bulgaria. The Struma Valley is heavily influenced by fault systems, including the Struma Fault. These faults create

zones of fracturing in the underlying bedrock, which can serve as conduits for groundwater movement. The presence of these fractured zones is critical for locating groundwater reserves.

The region, shares many of the geological characteristics of the broader region. However, it also has some unique features that are important for groundwater exploration and rainwater harvesting.

The municipality sits on a basement of metamorphic rocks, including gneisses, shists, and marbles.

Figure 1 shows the exact position of the measured ERT profile. As can be observed, it crosses the main contact between the different rock types – the metamorphic gneiss and the amphibolite gneiss.

Figure 1. Contact between the different rock types in the area of investigation

Figure 2. Geological situation around the area of investigation

Gneisses are high-grade metamorphic rocks, often highly folded and deformed due to tectonic pressures. Gneisses tend to be less permeable unless heavily fractured, which can limit groundwater storage in unfractured sections.

Schists are typically foliated and may host minor groundwater along fractures and joints. However, they are generally low in permeability.

Marble formations are particularly important for groundwater because they can develop karst features (dissolution cavities) that enhance permeability and water storage capacity.

The proximity of Strumyani to the Struma Fault means that the region is criss-crossed by fault lines, which have fractured the bedrock. These fault zones are often associated with increased permeability, creating potential conduits for groundwater flow.

In areas where the metamorphic bedrock is highly fractured, groundwater can accumulate in these fractures. However, these aquifers tend to be less productive than alluvial aquifers and may be more localised.

The alluvial deposits along the Struma River are the primary sources of groundwater. These aquifers are generally shallow but can provide significant quantities of water, especially in areas where the deposits are thickest.

Geophysical approach for sustainable groundwater

As Loke and his team (Loke, 2013) correctly stated, the resistivity survey method is one of the oldest and most commonly used geophysical exploration technique. It is currently used in many different areas: hydrological (Page, 1968; Wilson

et al., 2006), environmental and engineering (Chambers et al., 2006; Dahlin, 2001; Rucker et al., 2010), archeological (Griffiths and Barker, 1994; Tsokas et al., 2008), and mineral exploration (Bauman, 2005; Dimovski, et. al., 2017b; Legault et al., 2008; White et al., 2001) surveys.

The subsurface geology of the area is composed of alluvial and colluvial sediments interspersed with older metamorphic rocks, including schists, gneisses, and marbles. The permeability of these rock types is critical for groundwater storage and movement. Schist and gneiss formations tend to have lower permeability, while fractured marbles and alluvial deposits provide better conditions for groundwater accumulation. As Williams and co-workers (Williams, et. al, 2005) stated, the infiltrating water collects in the regolith and then recharges the underlying bedrock aquifer. They also pointed out that bedrock aquifers consist of openings, voids, fractures, and other discontinuities that transmit water through the rock and serve to connect the bedrock system to the overlying regolith. Because regolith has a much higher storage capacity than bedrock, the regolith can be thought of as being a ground-water reservoir or “sponge” that feeds the underlying bedrock discontinuities. This is the case in the village of Mahalata, where the upper position amphibolite gneisses provides good conditions for groundwater accumulation.

Figure 3 shows the exact position of the measured ERT line which is at a close distance from measured area.

Figure 3. Position of the ERT line

As Tomova stated (Tomova and Kisyov, 2024b), geophysical methods are commonly used for rapid data acquisition, allowing for efficient coverage of extensive areas in a cost-effective manner. Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) is used for this research due to its ability to provide detailed imaging of subsurface structures, which is essential for groundwater exploration. It is non-invasive and detailed subsurface mapping technique that allows for the identification of subsurface layers and structures without the need for drilling or excavation. This is especially important in areas where preserving the landscape is crucial, or where the cost of invasive methods is prohibitive.

ERT measures the electrical resistivity of the subsurface,

which varies based on the presence of water, rock types, and porosity. Water-bearing zones (such as aquifers) typically have lower resistivity than dry areas or bedrock, making it easier to identify potential groundwater deposits.

In the Petrich region, which features a mix of metamorphic rocks and sedimentary deposits, ERT can differentiate between various geological formations. It helps detect fractures, faults, or permeable layers where groundwater might accumulate, crucial for areas like Mahalata with its faulted geology.

By mapping resistivity contrasts, ERT can reveal areas where rainwater may infiltrate and accumulate, aiding in the

identification of recharge zones. This is particularly useful for sustainable water management and well-drilling planning.

This geological framework suggests that groundwater in the region is largely dependent on fractures and fault zones, where rainwater infiltration can contribute to aquifers.

Figure 4. Geophysical ERT profile

The second part of the line is presented by low resistivity values, in the upper part of the line. This part of the profile can be considered as potential groundwater aquifers. It lays down to the contact between the different rock types – metamorphic gneiss and the amphibolite gneiss.

As Tomova stated (Tomova & Kisyov 2024b), ERT is a non-invasive technique, and it can be deployed without disturbing the surface or subsurface. ERT offers a relatively cost-effective way to cover larger areas compared to traditional drilling methods, allowing for a broader survey and minimising the number of test wells needed. ERT's ability to detect variations in subsurface resistivity makes it an invaluable tool for identifying groundwater, characterising geological structures, and understanding the hydrological potential of the region.

Conclusion

The geology of the research region in the vicinity of Strumyani Municipality and the broader southwestern Bulgarian region is characterised by a complex interplay of metamorphic rocks, faulting, and alluvial deposits. These geological features create a variety of hydrogeological settings, including fractured bedrock aquifers and alluvial aquifers. Understanding these geological features is essential for effective groundwater exploration and sustainable water resource management. Additionally, alternative sources, like surface water, thermal springs, and rainwater harvesting could supplement local water supplies, providing a multi-faceted approach to addressing the region's water challenges. Geophysical techniques, especially Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT), offer crucial insights for hydrogeological research by enabling detailed subsurface mapping in a non-invasive manner.

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Figure 4 presents the measured electrical resistivity line. As can be observed, there is a clear division in the middle of the line. The ERT line crosses a large fracture zone in its first half. This zone is determined by a significant difference in elevation levels and slightly higher values of electrical resistivity on both two sides of the fracture zone.

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